

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part I

R. R. ASTIK, G. B. JOSHI and K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 18 March 1975; revised 10 June 1975; accepted 13 June 1975

Substituted thiazolidinones are prepared from 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone. The Schiff bases of substituted amines (aromatic) are prepared by the use of zinc chloride as a catalyst. These bases are then condensed with thioglycolic acid to get the thiazolidinones.

THIAZOLIDINONES are well known for their amoebicidal¹, anticonvulsant and anaesthetic² properties. It has been studied that anti-thyroid activity can be increased or decreased by introducing some groups in the structure³ and this type of drugs are also been tested against electric shock effects in mice³. We have prepared 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl)phenyl-3-aryl thiazolidinones by condensing thioglycolic acid with hydroxy keto-anils. The keto anils were prepared by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone with various aromatic amines in the catalytic presence of fused zinc-chloride at an elevated temperature ranging from 145° to 185° for 15 min. The ketone was obtained by Fries Migration of *p*-cresyl acetate⁴. Surrey and Cutler¹ prepared thiazolidinones by condensing the carbonyl component, the amine and thioglycolic acid in benzene for a long time. Raval and Trivedi^{5,6} also synthesised thiazolidinones by condensing aldehyde/ketone, amine and thioglycolic acid in benzene media by refluxing the contents for 5 to 7 hr. We have observed that the thiazolidinones can be conveniently synthesised from Schiff-bases and thioglycolic acid in benzene medium for a very short condensation time. The hypothesis that the first step of the reaction is the formation of an azo-methine is supported by our work. Besides the impurities of the ketones which do not form bisulfite adducts can also be easily avoided as the intermediate Schiff-bases of the ketones are separated. The ketoanils and the thioglycolic acid (1:1.1M) in benzene gave the products within 3 hr. The acetyl and benzoyl derivatives of the thiazolidinones and the compounds are recorded in Table I.

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by the method of Joshi *et al.*⁷ Aniline (0.58M) was condensed with 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone (0.50M) in the presence of the traces of fused zinc-chloride. The mixture was heated in an oil bath at 185° for 15 min, cooled taken in chloroform and filtered to remove zinc chloride-amine complex which is insoluble in chloroform. The evaporation of chloroform gave crude ketoanil. This on crystallization from ethanol (95%) gave yellow crystals, m.p. 112°. Yield 67%.

The thiazolidinones

The preparation of 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl)phenyl-3-phenyl thiazolidinone

The ketoanil (0.1M) was taken in dry benzene (50 ml.) To this was added thioglycolic acid (0.1M)

TABLE I—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE:

No.	R	Der. R'	m.p. °C	% N	
				Calc.	Found
1.	H	H	78	4.68	4.72
2.	H	Bz	118	3.47	3.50
3.	H	Ac	62	4.10	4.25
4.	Cl	H	115	4.20	4.34
5.	Cl	Bz	79	3.20	3.20
6.	Cl	Ac	260	3.72	3.95
7.	Br	H	131	3.70	3.89
8.	Br	Bz	140	2.91	3.00
9.	Br	Ac	125	3.33	3.56
10.	CH ₃	H	158	4.47	4.58
11.	CH ₃	Bz	300(d)	3.36	3.42
12.	CH ₃	Ac	145	3.94	4.00
13.	OCH ₃	H	151	4.25	4.30
14.	OCH ₃	Bz	112	3.23	3.30
15.	OCH ₃	Ac	180(d)	3.77	3.80

and the contents of the flask were refluxed in a water bath for 3 hr. The contents were cooled, poured in water, the upper organic layer washed with NaHCO₃ solution and water. This was dried with Na₂SO₄ and benzene was distilled off at reduced pressure. The

residue on crystallization from ethanol (95%) imparted the thiazolidinone, m.p. 78°. Yield 65%.

The other title compounds were prepared by the same method. The acetyl and benzoyl derivatives were prepared by the usual Schoutaon-Bauman method.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank Saurashtra University for research facilities and to CSIR, New Delhi for a junior research fellowship to RRA.

References

1. A. R. SUREVY and R. A. CUTLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 578.
2. H. D. TROUTMAN and LOREN M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **66**, 329.
3. L. P. DAMKIV and M. S. AVGOSINOVICH, *Zb. Nauk. Pratis. L'Vivs'k Med. Inst.*, 1963, **24**, 58.
4. K. FRIES, *Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 717.
5. B. K. RAVAL and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 353.
6. B. K. RAVAL and J. J. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 3.
7. G. B. JOSHI, Ph.D. Thesis, Gijarat University, 1971.